

ABOUT URSAL: UNION OF SOCIALIST REPUBLICS OF LATIN AMERICA

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ABSTRACT

This essay deals with an expensive and complex subject that tries to maintain an aura of secrecy about it, given its ambitious scope. The subject is the idea of transforming Latin America into a single bloc under the socialist regime, on the model of the former Soviet Union. The problem comes up against the question of which country would assume the central command of this group, highlighting that the one with the greatest economic power is little more organized than a German dump and the one with the greatest intellectual capacity does not have management conditions because of its condition. miserable. It is an essay drawn from empirical knowledge about socialism and its inevitable ills that do not take long to appear, as soon as the regime is implemented over the nation. Where the socialist regime was implemented, what was seen was chaos taking care of everything and everyone, in which for a short period one experiences a state of euphoria and excessive spending, believing that everything will last forever. Che Guevara's big dream was to create the Union of Socialist Republics of Latin America (URSAL). However, before uniting them under this role, it was necessary to turn the democratic republics into socialist republics, whether through a military coup or through local revolutions; the means used to achieve the desideratum did not matter; in the end, the ends would justify the means. URSAL's desire is to create a private backyard, from which they can extract their personal interests. The formation of an integrated society in Latin America is an old dream that was tried by brute force, by the bullet and by convincing the public that only the left cares about the people, not just the poor anymore, because they discovered, over the years that, without money, it is impossible to make any revolution. To everyone's happiness, all attempts to carry out such an undertaking ended up failing, vehemently.

Keywords: Latin America. URSAL. Socialism. Consequences of Socialism.

INTRODUCTION

Before having a collective united in favor of the same political principle, it is necessary for it to be united within the same and unique ideological principle. The motto of every dictatorial system is 'either you are with me, or you are against me!' This is because these

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individuals cannot bear doubt and the simple idea that they will have to face life in its harshness and the wrath of all those they have harmed, in the name of grandiose feelings, already makes them go into a state of panic. . Not only are tyrannical leaders paranoid, given that they are, *par excellence* , sociopaths and marked by profound traits of psychopathy; but, the whole system becomes sick with nerves in a relatively short time, through the ideological propaganda that aliens are trying to take everything they have. The aliens are represented by the leaders and businesspeople of capitalist countries.

Thus, anyone who begins to question the *modus operandi* of the governance in office is immediately hunted down and subjected to forced disappearance and, if it is an individual who tends towards the opposing political leadership, before disappearing from the map, he is subjected to mockery and public depreciation regarding his character and his *real intentions* in relation to the people and the Homeland. It is with the aim of guaranteeing happiness and social well-being that the regime fights its enemies [*real and imaginary*] who, by extension, are opponents of the people. As a rule, it is always in the name of goods considered noble and elevated, the product of a moralizing and destructive education, such as the Platonic one, which has been applied, especially in the West, that indoctrination and preparation are achieved for individuals to come to be seduced by socialist ideology without making much effort.

It was like this in the Soviet regimes, in which the purges of the priest Yoseph Stalin (1878-1953) were all in the name of the well-being of the nation, in order to ensure that the enemies of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics did not destroy everyone's dream, achieved with so much effort. Driven by this thought, many family members denounced relatives; friends betrayed friends; students denounced their teachers, wives denounced their husbands. And, there was no feeling of regret for the future fate of the betrayed convict, because the nation and its ideals were above any emotional bond that could be thought to exist with their contemporaries. I remember a professor who taught at an important university in Cuba and who gathered a group of students at his home to talk about politics and changes in the government structure and who ended up being denounced, by his own wife, as a subversive of the Establishment ; As a result, he was impeached and expelled from his country.

When the Cuban Revolution took place, with the takeover of the Moncada Cartel, on January 1, 1959, in which Fidel Castro, together with Ernesto Che Guevara, Raul Castro and Camilo Cienfuegos assumed total control of the Island, everything seemed to go very smoothly, with Fidel taking power as president and strongly aligned with the United States of America, both ideologically and politically.

It turns out that, in the course of the Castro administration, the young president began to transform himself into a dictator and apply ideas from the Bolshevik Revolution (1917), carrying out an extensive expropriation of land, especially from North American landowners, many of them with positions in Congress and the Senate of the United States of America. This was how, in 1961, an attack took place against the Nation of Cuba, with the objective being to remove the Castro Family from power; however, what was surreptitious was the interest of American producers, businessmen and politicians in having their assets and properties confiscated by the new government returned.

The invasion fails, especially because from that moment on, each citizen summoned was defending something that was theirs, no longer someone else's property, and, to help in the battle, the Commander in Chief himself, Fidel Castro, went to the battlefield to lead his troops. soldiers under his direct command.

Humiliated, American congressmen needed to create a new strategy to justify belligerent action against the Commander of Cuba: they claimed that the Soviet Union had set up a missile base in Cuba, with some of them aimed directly at the USA. The interest was to move the American people, so that they would ask for state military intervention against the neighbor who usurped other people's properties from a few Americans. None of this has proven to be true and what remains is a matter of meaningless studies, like a lie that must continue to be told in order to praise diplomats who have never done anything useful to anyone.

In this sense, the figure of Ernesto Guevara was relegated to a guerrilla fighter who is only admired in Cuba. Argentinian, a doctor by training, Che spent a good part of his life searching for meaning, which he only found in the midst of war. Before meeting with Fidel Castro Ruz, in Mexico, the country where he was exiled after a failed coup attempt against the government of Fulgêncio Batista, Guevara had lived on adventures in Central America, caring for lepers, but he did not leave any clinical-medical treatises about his work and the results achieved with his patients. He had lived as a beggar in Miami (USA), where his family in Argentina had to send them resources so that he would not die in poverty.

By meeting with the revolutionaries and drawing up plans to take over Cuba, his life had a meaning, he had found what he had *always* been looking for: an ideal that would produce the adrenaline rush he needed for his happiness. And so it was while the seizure of power lasted! At the end of his journey, he felt so lost that he jumped from one branch to another in federal administrative positions, producing nothing effective in any of them, the only achievement for which he is remembered during his time at the Ministry of the Sugar Industry was that of *creation of voluntary work*.

In the meantime of dissatisfaction and uneasiness with peaceful life, the idea of transforming all of Latin America into a socialist conglomerate came into his head: the Union of Socialist Republics of Latin America – URSAL, similar to what Russia had done with the Eastern Europe, at the beginning of the 20th century.

The idea was attractive to everyone, especially to Moscow and, even more so, to La Habana, which would be the great epistemological and administrative epicenter of the entire Latin American conglomerate dominated by Leninist-Marxist socialism. As it is a very large region with very varied cultures, there would have to be a strategy for taking over the region; but, Ernesto Guevara felt the need for war, his spirit was not something trained to the point of negotiating a political takeover; His objective and desire were to take over the region and unify it through unmeasured brute force. Fail! And this happens precisely because the people of the region were not interested in being freed from any condition of oppression.

Ernesto Rafael Guevara de la Serna is captured and killed on October 9, 1967, in Bolivia. However, his ideal of unifying Latin America under the banner of socialist idealism (URSAL) survived, in silence, in the person of a political genius and strategist, Fidel Castro Alejandro Ruz who, with the end of the Military Government Regime in Brazil, created, together with others, in 1990, the *São Paulo Forum*, which had, under the euphemism of promoting Latin American integration in the economic, political and cultural sphere, resurrected the idea of URSAL.

If anyone dares to believe that this idea was born with this group, this year, just read the sole paragraph of Article 4 of the 1988 Federal Constitution, which reads: “The Federative Republic of Brazil will seek the economic, political, social and cultural integration of the peoples of Latin America, aiming at the formation of a Latin American community of nations” (BRASIL, 1988, sp).

In a very subtle way, Brazil was forced to share this insanity that did not work anywhere in the world and, when the team integrated into the São Paulo Forum came to power or took it, regardless of the paths used to do so, there would be no who could stop the inordinate measures carried out by the Nation's commanders. One thing is a fact, this group thinks with extreme longevity and patience is one of its greatest virtues. No *wonder*, they have been gaining a huge space in society, convincing the majority that their purpose is the well-being of the Nation and that everything they do is aimed at improving the social conditions of existence of the population and, contrary to their speech of peace and love, everything they do that is bad and perverse is a way of protecting the people from individuals who do not have the proper understanding of the mission that belongs to the leaders and who, with their perverse actions

awaken chaos and insecurity. They are based on the Newtonian principle of the law of action and reaction, in which, for each action, a reaction of the same intensity occurs; however, the reaction of this group is excessively paranoid, which already demonstrates that their processes of understanding what democracy is is, in fact, relative; in other words, faced with a manifestation inherent to the existence of the democratic principle, which is the freedom to express thoughts contrary to its dictates, the use of unmeasured brute force is justified, because the opponents [of Democracy (sic)] *must be fought* under iron and fire. Translation: they must be arrested... or killed!

URSAL'S DESIDERATO

URSAL's greatest desire is to create a private backyard, from which they can extract their personal interests. The formation of an integrated society in Latin America is an old dream and one that was attempted by brute force, through bullets and by convincing the public that only the left cares about the people, no longer just about the poor, because they discovered, over the years that, without money, it is impossible to make any revolution. To everyone's happiness, all attempts to carry out such an undertaking ended in vehement failure.

Guevara had advocated such an idea, based not only on the [*apparently*] successful example of Russia, which unified an entire conglomerate of countries and thus formed the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), but also that there existed an entire economic condition in which the circulating capital in the nations was huge, allowing super rich families to finance schizopathic incursions disguised as revolutionary ideals.

Fidel Castro Ruz became the rightful heir of Ernesto Guevara; however, his charisma, combined with his genius and patience in the game, made him understand very well that an action of such magnitude should come from the people, as if this desire were organic and not a bureaucratic imposition. To do this, some details would have to be adjusted that would make the journey less complex.

The first task is to force all families to send their children to schools, managed by the State from their maintenance to the content that would be taught to children and, in this educational training package, the main issue is not to say that the Socialism is the best form of government, the fairest, the most perfect. It is interesting to say that capitalism is man's great curse and the cause of all his unhappiness, because it provokes and imputes competition to everyone, making everyone look like different figures, highlighting this difference through individual conflicts and social inequality.

While Fidel Castro remained alive and the dream of URSAL remained a fetish linked to his image, nothing more natural than the capital of the new empire being the Caribbean country Cuba. Behold, with his death in 2016, since then no one has been willing to claim guidance for the formation of the socialist bloc until now, because Nicolás Maduro, dictator of Venezuela, has just called on his colleagues [still] presidents of South America, *calling* for them to form a group of countries under a single flag and, of course, he did not express this feeling, but, with his country as the official capital of this utopian [or *dystopian*] conglomerate and, as he is, officially, the president of Venezuela, he would, by extension, be the Commander in Chief of URSAL.

Nothing impossible for it to happen, in the short, medium or long term, in the way Maduro recommends. The only problem is that in his delusion of power, he intends to place URSAL under the intellectual and pragmatic domination of China and Russia, a common thing for him, because while Fidel was still alive, he went every week to meet with the Commander of Cuba, in order to take lessons in political and diplomatic administration (sic) from the former dictator. When Chávez died, Maduro talked to a bird, which he claimed was the incarnation of Hugo Chávez and, later, the dialogue took place with a cow, claiming the same thing.

As stated by Nicolás Maduro, URSAL will just be an immense storehouse of *commodities* and sources of industrial raw materials for China and Russia. The intention is to create a power, formed by several independent nations, that is under the imperial rule of a single nation. Strangest desire to be understood. It is no wonder when it is said that the political thought of these individuals is still stagnant in Feudalist Europe.

Every left-wing politician suffers from a very serious problem of egolatriy associated with egodystonism and, one of the things that they do not admit, under any circumstances, are evaluations regarding their governments, which always refer to them as great and/or excellent and all The measures they apply are wonderful, always aiming for the well-being of the people. For this notorious reason, they wish to perpetuate themselves in power *ad infinitum* .

If this insanity comes to fruition, it will be hell on Earth, because there will be Latin American nations that will resist voluntary participation in the URSAL bloc, which will only receive this title, in its complete performance, when all nations are added to the *bloc* . and, those who resist integration will be massacred, both economically and militarily, depending on the interests that arouse in the executioners on duty.

URSAL's interest is not the well-being of the Latin American and Caribbean people. It is the shortest path for Russia and China to take complete domination of the world, through the destruction of the North American economy. The darkest intentions remain obscure and no

matter how much you investigate, it is practically impossible to reach the heart of the desire that she holds as an ideal. Guevara was a hyperactive lunatic; However, his particular interest in the annexation of the Latin American bloc was that this would require a lot of field battles, a lot of war and blood to be shed, unique situations in which he felt alive. In fact, the bloody battlefield was the only place he could experience inner peace. The tension caused and the need to always be on high alert gave him the quantum of adrenaline and life that he required to be well emotionally.

Through the apparent utopia of the revolutionary, it was not difficult for the Soviet Empire to perceive a unique chance to have a colony at its disposal without the need to spend on maintenance and not suffer strain from resolving conflicts. The political instability in the region hindered Russia's plans and, possibly, the ruin of the Soviet bloc was another obstacle to the takeover of Latin America and, to make matters worse, it now has to be content with sharing the cake with China.

This condition of always needing greater leadership is typical of this group, which cannot think for itself, always depending on an intellectual mentor, a substitute for the *father* that they try so hard to ignore and claim that they have no use other than to show themselves as a dictator; therefore, *an emblematic figure* must be fought with all the violence that individual and collective neurosis allows. Under this mechanism of androgenic bankruptcy, on the part of socialist leaders, the countries of Latin America continue to be a conglomerate of political dissent, always disruptive and, to cover up their status as intellectual and pragmatic eunuchs, they place all the blame on political polarization, implying a dangerous, subliminal discourse that the solution to all the evils that appear to be obstacles to the region's development is the complete elimination of political opponents, which they euphemize and sublimate under the banner of ideological equality.

The political leadership linked to socialist thought has no other vision than their eternal perpetuation in power, keeping everyone below them, confined in their subservient conditions. For them, the people do not exist, only the Homeland and, while for the democratic ones, this is formed by the people and for the people; Therefore, the well-being of this is what gives shape to the nation, socialists try, at any cost, to save their most hidden interests, under the banner that certain agreements, until then treated as inappropriate matters and situations impossible to happen, be brought to the negotiation table.

An example of this was the *ghostly rapprochement*, much celebrated by the international press, between Cuba and the United States of America, marked by the visit of the American

President, in office at the time, Barack Obama to the Island. In the wake of the event, North American and Cuban embassies were opened in Washington DC and La Habana in 2016.

The real intention behind the rapprochement between Havana and Washington DC is the concern of the Communist Party of Cuba with the aging of its population, the reduction of its workforce and the evasion of young people to Miami, the Cuban stronghold in the USA. Since 1961, the North American government has introduced a subsidy for every Cuban citizen who takes refuge in the American city. Of course, there is a price to be paid for the fugitive welcomed: never, under any circumstances, praise the Island regime and the Castro Family. Anyone who disobeys this canonical rule is returned to their country of origin, living as a pariah, in conditions of absolute misery, counting on the mercy of their peers, since the State abandons them to their own fate, considering that it was he who, in the first place, had abandoned the State.

This condition of economic security offered to those who manage to escape socialist life in Cuba, by the USA, makes young people decide to leave and never return, which has weakened microeconomic production sectors. Therefore, the approach with the US government had the objective of ending this subsidy, making the escape to capitalist paradise a dream not as advantageous as it appears to be.

No action with apparent altruism that comes from a socialist regime has any intention of improving the lives of the people. Their interests are always in favor of the group that surrounds them, motivating their indefinite stay in power.

North-American President Barack Obama was not received by the Cuban Head of State at José Martí International Airport, in Havana, on the occasion of his arrival and this was very poorly seen by the international press and the Government Communication Secretariat clarified that a formal reception by the President Raul Castro at the landing site of the American delegation was not part of the agreement reached between the two nations.

It turns out that it is not a question of agreeing on a decent and honorable reception for a visit from a Head of State; the situation calls for a little courtesy and principles; However, the attitude already demonstrates that, even though there is a considerable range of Cubans living in the enemy nation, it continues to be a hindrance for communist leaders, clarifying that the visit was not at all cordial between the parties. The interest was hidden and direct. On the part of the Cuban Regime, it was already known that the economic embargo against the Caribbean nation would not be lifted.

The visit went within the expected parameters and everyone (press and Cuban leaders) was completely silent about the presence of the American President in the capital, until Obama

touched on a taboo subject for any communist: freedom of *expression* ! When he said, on the third day in the Capital La Habana, he would make free broadband internet available throughout the country, the red light went on at the front and it took no more than 16 hours for Fidel Castro Ruz to publish an article aimed at the then former -visitor to your country, that infinite achievements had been achieved by the Cuban people during all those more than 50 years, in which they were under a terrible economic embargo and could not ignore the advances in education, such as the eradication of illiteracy, medical discoveries, technical support and technology transfer to different countries around the world. With this, the entire proposal that had taken the American President to a historic visit to the Caribbean country was thrown in the trash can, without the slightest resentment towards the Cuban leader.

In 2015, an unusual event occurred, in which the Cuban government gave the people access to the world wide web through a card with 1 mega power. In a matter of hours, the cards were sold out and the people, with the help of TV Local, insulted the Minister, the Ministry of Communications and the government itself. The people's happiness did not last long and the government once again restricted access to the internet.

THE CONSEQUENCES OF SOCIALISM

Socialism, despite having a semantic radical that comes from a term that includes the idea of collectivity, its actions are, in every sense, of extreme particularity and aim at nothing more than the interests of collectives closed in on themselves. A group of enlightened people are imprisoned in an impenetrable dungeon, from where they observe the world in front of a mirror that reflects, solely and exclusively, what they believe to be absolute, irresolute and unquestionable truth.

One thing that needs to be understood, pertinently, is that a revolution does not happen by chance and, much less, without a plan drawn up in advance, listing the points that are deemed necessary to be fought with greater violence. It stands out among these points that some traditional elements that oppose the development plans of the government program must be eliminated; If this is not possible, they must be emasculated.

The first target of the socialist government regime is the traditional family and, by this term, let us understand, that which has the Father as the central figure of power. And why this individual? Because the State needs to assume itself as this central representative figure of power; Therefore, this being (the Father) must be emasculated, transformed into a eunuch, mutilated in its state of being, no longer seen as a becoming, because castrated and, just like

Osiris, of the Egyptian religion, it cannot be the guide of the generations to which he himself gave rise, as part of an immutable and irreplaceable biological process. The father can only live in the obscurity of the State, which becomes the great provider and the one who determines and directs the destiny of all citizens. In a very short time, he is not even a provider anymore, because the Socialist State starts to guarantee the livelihood of everyone, without distinction. This last condition represents the coup de grace for the paternal ego, which becomes nothing more than a court jester.

Then, they prevent each individual from becoming an entrepreneur, through a discourse of unique equality that, in the wake, has the State definitively prohibiting the individual entrepreneurial spirit, because this produces and highlights social inequality. This attitude, which seems insane, causes the entire context to deteriorate and, in a short time, this begins to be understood as a mechanism for maintaining social order: the preservation of socialism, as an ideal government regime, depends on this condition of collective inertia. , shortly before individual.

The big problem has been that they are trying to see socialism as a barbaric and mystical condition, as portrayed in history books about the metamorphosis caused in Russian society, starting with the Bolshevik Revolution (October 1917), in which all assets were kidnapped. of their owners and distributed, without any technical criteria, feeding the ideology that everyone is equal; therefore, they are holders of equal rights and, if nature does not promote this, it is up to the State to do so.

As communist thought matured, its theories evolved to the point that the way to make everyone equal is through the use of law. No leader or political leader, in their right mind, would dare to prohibit a family from renovating their home; however, he may claim that, to do so, he must obtain a license from the body or department responsible for this and, in the process, this *legal authorization* is delayed until individuals completely lose interest in the reform. With such an attitude, the State does not appear to be totalitarian but rather bureaucratic, making everyone hate bureaucracy, *since* abusive authoritarian control hides in the shadows of bureaucratic issues created by State agents with specific purposes.

The State, which, in its political capacity, is a regulatory, supervisory agent and provider of essential services, transforms itself into a producer and, at the same time, into a generator of jobs, concerned about the unemployment rates that are plaguing the market. As a result, the services provided become more precarious and, consequently, the subsidies offered are crushed, turning professional careers in the public sector into despicable things; However, there is one condition that still attracts candidates to this infamous vice: career stability.

Trapped by this idea, they give themselves up to a miserable life amidst figures who are manipulated by the socialist *establishment*, full of fanatics zealous for order who see any act of dissatisfaction as a serious offense against the established order and, from this, persecution. This apostate has [*only*] a beginning, with there being no longer any way to defend himself from his tormentors, leaving him to renounce that life of misery among miserable and dangerous individuals who, in the name of their beliefs, would even kill one, before, friend.

The socialist is not a structure that presents itself in a solid way to the unwary eye, precisely because it was by not considering the human element and its nuances, such as sociological and geographical conditions, that the former USSR project was not more successful. Here, in this work, I list 5 (five) points that determine a society consumed by communist ideology and that, once thought is established and fixed as a causal relationship of natural forces, the destiny of such a nation is, to live, eternally enslaved; because the sheep's spiritual feelings start to be transmitted through phylogenetic inheritance, that is, the individual born in the communist universe starts to repeat the behavior of the herd.

THE 5 POINTS THAT CHARACTERIZE A SOCIETY CONSUMED BY SOCIALIST IDEOLOGY

The fact of determining something in science is a matter of clarifying, through data gathering, points that represent the entire process or target object of analytical study, to which a description is applied after having interpreted its psychology. It is not written in any table of law that there are no more elements that demonstrate the subversiveness of socialism. It turns out that propaganda cannot be very extensive, running the risk of losing its ideological and methodological essence of indoctrination and demonization of a certain enemy always lurking around the human spirit: social inequality, which has been largely responsible for human unhappiness and by the countless wars that ravage humanity. This hides the metaphor that, in an economically competitive environment, no one is happy, because there will always be someone who has more than their neighbor and this, in turn, cannot purchase the product that is causing their anguish.

To get around the problem, the solution is to rely on the rhetoric that everyone is equal and this is what the Savior determined, despite the fact that, behind the scenes, they despise religion. Behind all this, they implant fear in the population that, if the regime falls, social inequality will take its place and someone will have more goods than the other and, thus, the people themselves start to fight so that everyone remains immersed in the misery. Once the

entrepreneurial feeling has been devastated from the individual's thinking, what remains for him is to fight for everything to remain as it is...

Below, I list and describe the 5 characterizing points of Socialism in a society:

1st THE ILLUSION OF WEALTH AND SOCIAL EQUALITY

As the first point to win over believers to the new religion called socialism, the proposal is to produce the illusion of social equality through the acquisition of consumer goods. As almost no one has enough credit to spend on superfluous things, lines of credit are opened through an autophagic state system; but, how imperceptible to the common citizen, because they are alienated by the possibility of having their own car, plasma television, state-of-the-art telephone, even though these useful goods are completely useless to them from an economic point of view.

As the process continues, it becomes mandatory for all children to attend school, preferably public school, as this is where the State is best able to co-opt students into its religion and create a sect of highly obedient and faithful fanatics. to socialist principles. All conditions of conflict and competitiveness are being eliminated from this environment, in the name of equality and *non-discrimination of any kind* . This causes the feeling of entrepreneurship, an inherent part of the human condition, to be tamed and, little by little, it ceases to exist, giving rise to the explicit desire to become a public agent and not an entrepreneur.

Within theoretical thinking, the simple fact that the student is there is enough to justify their patriotic spirit; therefore, he cannot be failed if he has not reached the average determined in the curriculum for his school approval, since this would cause trauma to the individual and would represent an injustice against the individual, since the time spent in his life was equal (sic) to that of the colleague who did better.

In sporting and even literary competitions, one can no longer privilege those who excelled in the modalities, since the *important thing is not to win; but, participate!* Thus, as the moment cannot go unnoticed, everyone will receive a prize, proving that there is no longer any derogatory merit in relation to those who failed to achieve the best results.

Over time, this group starts to cower in the face of life and, surreptitiously, the harmful idea that social equality is something artificial that is promoted by the State and its active policies (sic) takes over their thoughts. Therefore, they must fight to maintain this State model so that their children and grandchildren do not suffer from the vicissitudes of a State and a society determined by oppression and symbolic violence.

Not satisfied, the ideologues of the Socialist State create mechanisms that enable a large mass of people to enter Universities and have access to Higher Education, with the promise that only education sets men free and with the possession of a university degree the possibilities of employment become larger; but, in the process, they forget the law of supply and demand and, I'm not talking about the professional once graduated, but rather, the need for properly qualified teachers to transform the mass of students into skilled professionals to perform the functions as such. As they never match the market, the result of this entire university panacea is a contingent of graduates working in underemployment, increasingly unhappy and who are prohibited from criticizing the State's educational policies; because it was thanks to them that he got a place at the university he *dreamed of* and was able to become a holder of a higher degree.

All of the individual's merit is set aside and subjugated, not to say suppressed. Everything he achieved was due to the State's initiative and its affirmative actions. Ingratitude against the State is not permitted in a socialist system! It's sacrilege! And the sacrilegious must be punished in an exemplary manner! And, this occurs through social exclusion; this individual is banned from social conventions, becoming a match... He is left with three real options: either he surrenders to the system, kneeling and praying according to the imposed manual; suicidal or fleeing to a country that can be considered less contaminated by this plague.

2nd THE CONSOLIDATION OF THE DREAM OF SOCIAL EQUALITY THROUGH MISERY

As the state goes on a spree with the money saved for years, always alert to cataclysmic situations in which its intervention proves urgent and necessary, what remains is the condemnation to unprecedented poverty and, only then, in this existential state in which everyone, without distinction, can be equal, in a political regime that preaches indistinct equality. Everything that was achieved by the majority is being dissipated in exchange for conditions so as not to end up in a mass grave and, in a short time, this same majority that felt rich returns to its previous state of existence, with the aggravating factor that, if it was previously poor, now he is miserable, having to content himself with the thought of Francesca da Rimini (1255-1285) who said that, "there is nothing more painful in life than remembering the glory days in misery"!

In order to keep the people alienated, the *establishment* creates a villain who shows himself as not only the cause of this situation but also responsible for its perpetuation: Capitalism, which preaches social inequality through the accumulation of goods in the hands

of a few . individuals. So, a capitalist entrepreneur who generates a thousand jobs would do more good for society if he sold all his goods and shared them with the poor, because then, there would be a thousand and one happy individuals... in a short time, there would be a thousand and one in the state begging queue. They take for themselves the jargon of the largest commercial company in history, the Catholic Church, such as that money and wealth do not bring happiness; and, it is in poverty that Christ manifests himself; there subverted by the socialist regime as it is in the condition of misery that solidarity manifests itself; that is, men become fraternal among themselves. In the end, they say they are atheists, but they use the same rhetorical bizarreness as the infamous Christians to subject the people to a state of existential decadence.

No one dares to raise a voice against them, because when he thinks about doing so, an indoctrinating and absolutist conscience invades his thinking and reminds him that, under another regime, he would not be who he is! In other words, he owes his individual and professional identity to the Socialist Regime! This devotion is worth your silence, absolutely! This already proves that not only the individual's body is dominated by the *establishment*, but also his entire being, even his thoughts.

3rd THE EXPLORATION OF SOCIAL MISERY

As is only natural to happen, where there is poverty there will be exploitation, causing people to give in to their lowest instincts and the most vile activities, things they would never do in a normal social security situation. Every socialist says he is very liberal regarding customs, especially when it comes to sex; but, when discussing the subject of prostitution, it is a *taboo* and the mere fact of thinking about it is reason for a forced silence on the sacrilegious person who dared to mention, at least one case. This is a problem in capitalist countries, where savage capitalism has corrupted the spirit of youth, contaminating it with consumerist feelings and, as it is unable to obtain what it wants, it *indulges* in low attitudes and of little moral value.

It happened in a socialist country that underage student girls started prostituting themselves and, at first, they left school, went home and changed their clothes for the task. At one time, these teenagers didn't even change their uniforms for formal clothes to go and perform their programs with clients. This caused indignation among a university professor who decided to bring the problem to the attention of the High Commissioner during a Party meeting, and the result was that this professor *disappeared* and no one ever dared to ask about him, much less bring up the subject he had presented at that meeting.

Everyone turns a blind eye to the problem, because beauty products, such as shampoo, conditioner, soaps, nail polish, cost up to 60% of a typical employee's allowance. In a capitalist country, what are considered basic health and aesthetic items, in socialist countries, this is something of extreme luxury, making access to citizens through ordinary means almost impossible.

The termination of pregnancy is something deliberate between the patient and her partner, and the medical board is not subject to any type of constraint, of any nature, on the person who decides to do so. The family also does not interfere, because its power has already been taken away by the State and this is the rule that has been adopted as the ideal model for a society that seeks happiness, *eudaimonia* ; therefore, there can be no interference with this idyllic model of society.

So, if a young woman, even a teenager, becomes pregnant by a client, the solution is the easiest to think of, because there will be no question of any kind about the paternity of the purged child. In the same vein, cases of pedophilia, rape and other atrocities end without being publicly revealed. And, if he does, whoever makes the complaint runs the serious risk of *disappearing*, because he exposed a type of morality that is not in line with socialist principles. Such actions are problems that affect the citizens of capitalist nations, who live under a libertine state, devoid of morals.

Slavery exploitation becomes a reality, because someone among them will have a little more and will tend to demand payments for the products and services provided, given that brotherhood and charity is nothing more than a figure of rhetoric used as ideological propaganda by the top management. of State. In the midst of the world of the living, where reality is cruel and bloodthirsty, the law of survival [*at any cost*] is what determines existence. Individuals return to the savage state portrayed by Hobbes (1588-1679), in his work *The Leviathan* , with the difference that, in this work, there is the thought that the State emerges to create and maintain the balance necessary for the existence of men. In Socialism, the State is the creator and maintainer of the bestial state in which the beast, disguised as human, manifests itself as the wolf of man.

And, if by chance, there is someone willing to ask whether the State does not know about these things occurring... the answer is, no! First, because he remains cloistered in a schizophrenic state in which he only sees and hears what his own gods reveal to him, and anyone who dares to say anything different from what he sees reflected in the mirror of his palace is condemned to ostracism, expiation and, if the symptom persists after purging.

So, all the information that reaches the leader (sic) is that everything is going in perfect order. This, in turn, instructs (sic) that his people lack nothing, so that they do not become unhappy and distressed; because, in your country, no one can be sad; everyone must smile; since, for them, a smile is the only reason for happiness.

Thefts and robberies become frequent, because of basic needs. Rural producers start spending on safety measures for their herds, putting a burden on their production systems. The State prevents citizens from consuming protein of animal origin, in a variety and quantity that is not offered by it itself. Even what can be consumed, in terms of food, becomes the responsibility of the Regime. Free trade in basic necessities is destroyed, leaving the people in a strange and difficult to understand situation.

Bribery becomes the current morality and situations of exchanging basic goods for essential services, a natural condition, with no type of control over this. It may seem absurd, but this relationship is between things that, in another situation, would seem superfluous and insignificant, such as a soap, a bar of soap, a chicken, a kilo of beans, rice, corn flour or cassava, fish, things that, for those in the field it is common. With this, the peasant citizen finds himself in a situation of greater advantage in relation to the urban citizen.

4TH SOCIAL EQUALITY CAMUFLAGED THROUGH THE INFORMAL ECONOMY

One thing that is very prominent in socialist countries is *the black market*, whose euphemism is represented by the expression *informal market*. As everyone is afraid to send money to banks, since they are all state owned and, in addition to the interest rates being exorbitant, there is a risk of being perceived as a subversive agent and having assets seized, in the name of social equality. This means that most commercial transactions are carried out confidentially and outside the State, enabling parallel monetary circulation in incalculable quantities.

Everyone, without exception, maintains the ideology of the *vote of poverty*; but, in his particular state, he is a rich individual, living a naughty life in relation to his miserable compatriots. To give you an idea of what this represents when the former USSR fell, 40% of the *Soviet establishment's economy* was informal. Millionaires were discovered in the system where only miserable people should exist; There could not even be poor people, because the existence of this last group reveals the existence of social inequality.

All health agents are State employees; However, nothing prevents them from secretly helping someone in the dead of night and charging for their services. Through a silent scheme, an entire system of generating foreign currency is being set up, at the expense of those who are on the edge of existence; in the absence of the State, while it, sick of nerves and narcissistic, continues to admire its beauty and magnitude in front of a mirror that reveals to it what its pride wants to hear.

Private producers are obliged to *sell* their respective production, whether agricultural or industrial, to the State. Not that there are no people who want to buy directly, but this is the policy defined by the Regime. Anyone who produces protein of animal origin, such as eggs, milk, meat, cannot simply kill an ox on their property and offer a barbecue, or even consume the meat of the bull that was fattened by them, on their land. As they are all equal, without any type of distinction, it is right for you to sell your ox to the State and go get your portion at the municipal market, like all other citizens. Social equality is an element taken very seriously in this political regime.

5TH DEFINITIVE LOSS OF INDIVIDUAL ENTREPRENEURIAL FEELING

After everything listed and discussed above, the tendency is for the individual to lose all of his pro-activism, because nothing he does is worth social recognition and he still runs the risk of being punished by the State. Wealth and individual growth are now seen as risk factors to their security and that of their children and closest relatives.

A whole generation of young people who could have undertaken, through the creation of their own businesses, are co-opted into the grueling and lackluster public service, making them obscure bureaucratic figures, being forced to keep their respective conflict states secret from everyone, simply for fear of being denounced and, as a result, losing everything they have, because they have achieved nothing; everything was given to them by the Great Father, the State. There is no merit with which to celebrate in your entire life.

Over time, this existence, which passed without effort (sic) and without merit, becomes the great reality of an entire population and nothing is created or copied, ending up inert in the face of life. Socrates (470-399 BC) referred to this lifestyle as *no life at all* .

Even those who dedicated themselves to working in the field, in direct contact with nature and its challenging variants, after years of being forced to hand over the *results* of their work and efforts to someone who dictates the value of their products without any basis. on no criteria other than the ideology of the socialist regime and its fanatical proselytism, it stops

being enthusiastic and surrenders to the benefits of a Provider State, which produces nothing; it just hijacks what others produce and distributes it as if this were a representation of the most equitable justice known.

In socialist countries, no merit achieved can be an object of individual pride, because everything that was achieved was due to the fact that the Socialist State provided very special conditions for everyone, without distinction. Thus, an athlete who competes in an international tournament and emerges victorious, the prize received as part of the package does not belong to him. He must hand over everything to the State and the State takes care to apply its value, in a fair, equitable and egalitarian way for all the people.

There are two considerations for the State to assume this attitude: the first is that the talent that the athlete possesses is a natural, subjective ability; however, his technical improvement is due to the intervention of the State, which trained, prepared and projected him around the world. The second is that, if he keeps the prize and its value, this attitude triggers social inequality, as not everyone will have the same product. In the name of equality, everyone is condemned to the common grave of misery.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

What we sought to express in this essay is that URSAL (Union of Federative Republics of Latin America) is a still latent idea and that its emergence may cease to be a utopia, simply by convincing Brazil to be the great leader of this movement, something that until now has not been consolidated through a clear and defined position. History has already demonstrated that managing powers at long distance is a risky situation in the medium term; hence the reason why China and Russia are not so interested in taking over the leadership of the Country-Continent, as demonstrated by Nicolás Maduro's open desire, understood through his speech.

The problem that arises against the Latin American region is the intense political instability and a people who do not appear worthy of trust, in the sense of knowing what they think about each situation itself, with more opportunists than individuals committed to fighting for a ideal that you believe in and for which you are willing to sacrifice yourself.

History has already shown that the administration of territories located very far from decision-making domains is a risky condition in the medium term, hence why Russia and China remain cautious about an offensive in the region; not to mention that the hostile presence of the United States of America, just below, puts into question possible plans to take over Latin

America by the two powers. It is better to continue using the region as a breadbasket and supplier of high quality basic raw materials for the industry.

A point to be considered is that Brazil has not yet shown itself to be in favor of an effective alliance with the countries of Latin America, living as if it were a brother who ignores everyone else, and this situation is the great schism that has prevented establishment of URSAL since the creation of its idea, by Ernesto Guevara. What cannot be left aside is the existence of the desire for its establishment and, contrary to what many people think, it is not enough for the left to take over the leadership of Brazil, there must be a desire on the part of the leaders themselves to assume such political responsibility.

The 1988 Federal Constitution, while representing a coup d'état against Brazilian national sovereignty, is also a paradox; because, in its scope, it empowers congressmen to prevent any sudden movement that could harm the giant's beauty sleep, lying eternally in a splendid cradle.